

Solid angle subtended by a rectangular right pyramid (solid/hollow) at its apex

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Introduction: Here we are to derive the formula for finding out the solid angle subtended by a rectangular right pyramid at its apex by using formula of solid angle subtended by a rectangular plane at any point lying on the perpendicular passing through its centre which has already been derived in **HCR's Theory of Polygon** [1,2]. The solid angle subtended by a rectangular right pyramid will be derived in terms of apex angles α & β (i.e. angles between two pairs of consecutive lateral edges meeting at the apex of rectangular right pyramid).

Derivation: Let there be a right pyramid (solid or hollow) with apex point 'P' & base as a rectangle ABCD such that the angles between two pairs of consecutive lateral edges PA & PB and PB & PC are α and β respectively (as shown in the figure-1).

Now, drop the perpendiculars PO & PM on the rectangular base ABCD & side AB respectively & join the diagonals AC & BD of rectangular base ABCD (as shown by dotted lines in fig-1). Let a be the length of each of four equal lateral edges PA, PB, PC & PD of right pyramid.

In right $\triangle PMA$, (see triangular face APB of right pyramid in fig-1)

$$\sin \alpha \text{ APM} = \frac{AM}{AP} \Rightarrow \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} = \frac{AM}{a}$$

$$AM = a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

$$\therefore AB = CD = 2AM = 2a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

Similarly, in isosceles $\triangle PBC$, it can be proved by dropping a perpendicular from apex P to the side BC,

$$BC = AD = 2a \sin \frac{\beta}{2}$$

Using Pythagorean theorem in right $\triangle ABC$,

$$AC^2 = AB^2 + BC^2 = \left(2a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2}\right)^2 + \left(2a \sin \frac{\beta}{2}\right)^2 = 4a^2 \left(\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}\right)$$

$$AC = \sqrt{4a^2 \left(\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}\right)} = 2a \sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}}$$

$$AO = \frac{AC}{2} = \frac{2a \sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}}}{2} = a \sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}}$$

Using Pythagorean theorem in right $\triangle POA$ (see above fig-1),

$$PA^2 = AO^2 + PO^2 \Rightarrow PO = \sqrt{PA^2 - AO^2}$$

Figure 1: Perpendiculars PO & PM are dropped from apex P to the centre O of base ABCD & mid-point M of side AB in rectangular right pyramid

$$\begin{aligned}
PO &= \sqrt{a^2 - \left(a \sqrt{\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}} \right)^2} \\
&= a \sqrt{1 - \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}} \\
&= a \sqrt{\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the solid angle ($\omega_{pyramid}$) subtended by the rectangular right pyramid at its apex P will be equal to the solid angle ($\omega_{rectangle}$) subtended by rectangle ABCD of length and width l & b , at the apex P lying a normal height h from the centre 'O' which is given by the general formula of **HCR's Theory of Polygon** [1,2] as follows

$$\omega_{rectangle} = 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{lb}{\sqrt{(l^2 + 4h^2)(b^2 + 4h^2)}} \right)$$

Now, setting the value of normal height $h = PO$, length $l = AB$ & width $b = BC$ in the above general formula of solid angle, we get the solid angle subtended by the rectangular right pyramid at its apex

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega_{pyramid} &= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(AB)(BC)}{\sqrt{((AB)^2 + 4(PO)^2)((BC)^2 + 4(PO)^2)}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(2a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2})(2a \sin \frac{\beta}{2})}{\sqrt{\left((2a \sin \frac{\alpha}{2})^2 + 4 \left(a \sqrt{\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}} \right)^2 \right) \left((2a \sin \frac{\beta}{2})^2 + 4 \left(a \sqrt{\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2}} \right)^2 \right)}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{4a^2 \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2}}{\sqrt{(4a^2)^2 \left(\sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \left(\sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + \cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \right)}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2}}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \left(\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2}}{\sqrt{\left(\cos^2 \frac{\beta}{2} \right) \left(\cos^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \right)}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\frac{\sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2}}{\cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2}} \right) \\
&= 4\sin^{-1} \left(\tan \frac{\alpha}{2} \tan \frac{\beta}{2} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the **solid angle (ω) subtended at the apex by any right pyramid with a rectangular base & the apex angles α & β (i.e. angles between two pairs of consecutive lateral edges meeting at apex), is given by the following formula**

$$\omega = 4\sin^{-1}\left(\tan\frac{\alpha}{2}\tan\frac{\beta}{2}\right)$$

Where, $0 < \alpha + \beta < \pi$

Important deduction: The solid angle subtended at the apex by a right pyramid with a square base & the apex angle α is obtained by substituting $\beta = \alpha$ in above general equation of solid angle, we get

$$\omega = 4\sin^{-1}\left(\tan\frac{\alpha}{2}\tan\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)$$

$$\omega = 4\sin^{-1}\left(\tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)$$

Where, $0 < \alpha < \frac{\pi}{2}$

The above value of solid angle subtended at apex by a square right pyramid can also be proved by substituting $n =$ number of sides of square base $= 4$ in general formula of solid angle subtended at apex by a regular n -gonal right pyramid (which has been derived in the paper '**solid angle subtended by a regular n -gonal right pyramid at its apex**' by the author), given as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= 2\pi - 2n\sin^{-1}\left(\cos\frac{\pi}{n}\sqrt{\tan^2\frac{\pi}{n} - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 2(4)\sin^{-1}\left(\cos\frac{\pi}{4}\sqrt{\tan^2\frac{\pi}{4} - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) && \text{(setting } n = 4 \text{ for square base)} \\ &= 2\pi - 8\sin^{-1}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\sin^{-1}\left(2\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right)^2}\right) && \left(2\sin^{-1}x = \sin^{-1}(2x\sqrt{1-x^2})\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\sin^{-1}\left(2\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 - \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 + \tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\sin^{-1}\left(\sqrt{1 - \tan^4\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\cos^{-1}\left(\sqrt{1 - \left(\sqrt{1 - \tan^4\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right)^2}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\cos^{-1}\left(\sqrt{1 - 1 + \tan^4\frac{\alpha}{2}}\right) \\ &= 2\pi - 4\cos^{-1}\left(\tan^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 4 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \cos^{-1} \left(\tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right) \\
&= 4 \left(\sin^{-1} \left(\tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) \right) && \left(\text{Since, } \frac{\pi}{2} - \cos^{-1} x = \sin^{-1} x \right) \\
&= 4 \sin^{-1} \left(\tan^2 \frac{\alpha}{2} \right) && \text{Proved.}
\end{aligned}$$

Note: Above articles had been *derived & illustrated* by **Mr H.C. Rajpoot (M Tech, Production Engineering)**

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